

About Directed Fuzzing and Use-After-Free: How to Find Complex & Silent Bugs?

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Who Are We?

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What's The Talk About?

- Fuzzing is great for finding vulnerabilities in the wild
- Directed fuzzing is a slightly different setting
 - Goal = reach a specific target
 - Bug reproduction, patch-oriented testing
- The problem: Current fuzzing techniques are bad for some classes of issues
 - Here: “Use-After-Free” (UAF)
 - Important: sensitive info leaks, data corruption or first step to other attacks
- Proposal: A directed fuzzing approach tailored to UAF bugs
 - and applications to patch-oriented testing
 - and a tour on UAF and (directed) fuzzing

Use-After-Free

- Heap element is used after having been freed
- **Critical exploits** & serious consequences
 - Data corruption
 - Information leaks
 - Denial-of-service attacks

```
1 char *buf = (char *) malloc(BUF_SIZE);
2 free(buf); // pointer buf becomes dangling
3 ...
4 strncpy(buf, argv[1], BUF_SIZE-1); // Use-After-Free
```


UAF bugs in National Vulnerability Database

Teaser

```
1 int *p, *p_alias;
2 char buf[10];
3 void bad_func(int *p) {free(p);} /* exit() is missing */
4 void func() {
5     if (buf[1] == 'F')
6         bad_func(p);
7     else /* lots more code ... */
8 }
9 int main (int argc, char *argv[]) {
10     int f = open(argv[1], O_RDONLY);
11     read(f, buf, 10);
12     p = malloc(sizeof(int));
13     if (buf[0] == 'A'){
14         p_alias = malloc(sizeof(int));
15         p = p_alias;
16     }
17     func();
18     if (buf[2] == 'U')
19         *p_alias = 1;
20     return 0;
21 }
```

free

alloc

use

- PoC: 'AFU' → no crash
- Bug Target: 14 (alloc) → 17 → 6 → 3 (free) → 19 (use)
- Timeout: 6h

AFL-QEMU (binary)	AFLGo (source)	UAFuzz (binary)
✗ (6 hours)	✗ (6 hours)	✓ (~ 20 mins)

1. Context

-- about fuzzing, directed fuzzing

Code-level Flaws: Fuzzing is The New Hype

Project Springfield
Fuzz your code before hackers do

FUZZING.IO
Security Automation • Vulnerability Research

As Its Core, Fuzzing is Random Testing

-- and it starts a long time ago

- 1981 Random testing is a cost-effective alternative to systematic testing techniques (Duran & Natos)
- 1983 "The Monkey" (Capps)
- 1988 Birth of the term "fuzzing" (Miller)

Now: Three Shades of Fuzzing

Principle of Grey/Black Fuzzing

No Silver Bullet

Plateau phenomenon

```

4800 0000 5dc3 5589 e5c7 0812 0000 00b8 4800 0000 5dc3 558
0000 00b8 4500 0000 0820 0000 00b8 4500 000
b0e 0821 0000 00b0 0040 0000 0000 0000
e5c7 0540 bf0e 0822 0000 0000 0000 0000
5dc3 5589 e583 ec10 c705 0958 4900 0000 5dc3 5589 e583 ec1
0000 a148 bf0e 0803 f809 40ff 0e08 0100 0000 a148 bf0e 080
8b04 8548 e10b 08ff e0c6 0e97 0002 0000 8b04 8548 e10b 08ff
00c6 45f9 00c6 45f9 00c7 45f7 00c6 45f8 00c6 45f9 00c6 45f
0000 00e9 0901 0000 c645 0540 bf0e 0802 0000 00e9 0901 00
c645 f900 c645 fa01 807d f701 c645 f800 c645 f900 c645 fa0
40bf 0e08 0300 0000 807d f900 750a c705 480f 0e08 0300 000
fc00 750a c705 480f 0e08 f900 7410 807d fc00 750a c705 48b
fc00 7415 807d fb00 740f 0900 0000 807d fc00 7415 807d fb0
0000 0000 e908 0100 00e9 c705 480f 0e08 0000 0000 e908 010
f701 c645 f800 c645 f900 e000 0000 c645 f701 c645 f800 c64
fc00 740f c705 480f 0e08 c645 fa02 807d fc00 740f c705 48b
0100 00e9 0900 0000 c645 f800 0000 e05e 0100 00e9 0901 000
c645 f900 c645 fa03 807d f701 c645 f800 c645 f900 c645 fa0
fe00 750f c705 480f 0e08 fd00 7410 807d fe00 750a c705 48b
fc00 750f c705 480f 0e08 0500 0000 807d fc00 750a c705 48b
fe00 740f c705 480f 0e08 0300 0000 807d fe00 740f c705 48b
0190 0901 0000 c645 0600 0000 e90e 0100 00e9 0901 000
c645 f900 e000 807d f701 c645 f800 c645 f901 c645 fa0
480f 400 0000 c705 480f 0e08 df00 0000 c645 f701 c64
0000 c645 f701 c645 f809 0000 00e9 df00 0000 c645 f701 c64
fa04 807d fc00 7410 807d c645 0000 c645 fa04 807d fc00 741
480f 0e08 0700 0000 807d c645 0000 c645 fa04 807d fc00 741
ff00 740f c705 480f 0e08 fc00 7415 807d ff00 740f c705 48b
0000 00e9 0900 0000 c645 0000 0000 e90e 0000 00e9 0900 000
c645 f900 c645 fa05 807d 0000 0000 e90e 0000 00e9 0900 000
fc00 750a c705 480f 0e08 fd00 7410 807d fe00 750a c705 48b
fc00 750a c705 480f 0e08 f900 7410 807d fe00 750a c705 48b
fc00 750a c705 480f 0e08 f900 7410 807d fe00 750a c705 48b
fc00 7505 807d ff00 740c 0900 0000 807d fc00 7505 807d ff0
0000 0000 eb49 eb49 c645 c705 480f 0e08 0000 0000 eb49 eb4
c645 f901 c645 fa02 807d f701 c645 f800 c645 f901 c645 fa0
5dc3 5589 e5c7 0540 bf0e 0800 0000 00b8 4800 0000 5dc3 558
1800 0000 5dc3 5589 e5c7 0812 0000 00b8 4800 0000 5dc3 558
3000 00b8 4500 0000 5dc3 0540 bf0e 0820 0000 0000 0000
b0e 0821 0000 00b0 3800 3300 e5c7 0540 bf0e 0821 0000 0000
e5c7 0540 bf0e 0822 0000 0000 5dc3 5589 e5c7 0540 bf0e 082
5dc3 5589 e583 ec10 c705 0958 4900 0000 5dc3 5589 e583 ec10
3000 a148 bf0e 0803 f809 40ff 0e08 0100 0000 a148 bf0e 080
3b04 8548 e10b 08ff e0c6 0e97 0002 0000 3b04 8548 e10b 08ff
30c6 45f9 00c6 45f9 00c7 45f7 00c6 45f8 00c6 45f9 00c6 45f
3000 00e9 0901 0000 c645 0540 bf0e 0802 0000 00e9 0901 00
e0c6 45f9 00c6 45f9 00c7 45f7 00c6 45f8 00c6 45f9 00c6 45f
480f 0e08 0300 0000 807d f900 750a c705 480f 0e08 0300 000
e0c6 45f9 00c6 45f9 00c7 45f7 00c6 45f8 00c6 45f9 00c6 45f
fc00 750a c705 480f 0e08 f900 7410 807d fc00 750a c705 48b
fc00 7415 807d fb00 740f 0900 0000 807d fc00 7415 807d fb0
6000 0000 e908 0100 00e9 c705 480f 0e08 0000 0000 e908 010

```


Complex Code Structure

Complex Bugs

Target-oriented Testing?

Directed Greybox Fuzzing (DGF)

- Input: code + target (trace, code location)
- Goal = Cover the target
- AFLGo (2017), Hawkeye (2018)
- Applications:
 - Bug reproduction
 - Patch-oriented testing
 - Static analysis report confirmation

Coverage-guided Greybox Fuzzing **AFL**

Directed Greybox Fuzzing **AFLGo, Hawkeye**

2. Back to Use-After-Free (UAF)

Why is Detecting UAF Hard for Fuzzing?

- **Rarely found by fuzzers**
 - **Complexity:** 3 events in sequence spanning multiple functions
 - **Temporal & Spatial constraints:** extremely difficult to meet in practice
 - **Silence:** no segmentation fault

UAF bugs found (**1%**) by OSS-Fuzz in 2017

Recall: Motivation

```
1 int *p, *p_alias;
2 char buf[10];
3 void bad_func(int *p) {free(p);} /* exit() is missing */
4 void func() {
5     if (buf[1] == 'F')
6         bad_func(p);
7     else /* lots more code ... */
8 }
9 int main (int argc, char *argv[]) {
10     int f = open(argv[1], O_RDONLY);
11     read(f, buf, 10);
12     p = malloc(sizeof(int));
13     if (buf[0] == 'A'){
14         p_alias = malloc(sizeof(int));
15         p = p_alias;
16     }
17     func();
18     if (buf[2] == 'U')
19         *p_alias = 1;
20     return 0;
21 }
```

- PoC: 'AFU' → no crash
- Bug Target: 14 (alloc) → 17 → 6 → 3 (free) → 19 (use)
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AFL-QEMU (binary)	AFLGo (source)	UAFuzz (binary)
(6 hours)	(6 hours)	(~ 20 mins)

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3. UAFuzz: Directed Fuzzing for UAF

Existing DGF: #1 No Ordering & No Prioritization

Existing DGF: #2 Crash Assumption

Overview of UAFuzz [tailor every fuzzing step to UAF]

Key Insights of UAFuzz

- ★ Seed Selection: based on **similarity** and **ordering** of input trace
- ★ Power Schedule: based on 3 **seed metrics dedicated to UAF**
 - **[function level] UAF-based Distance**: Prioritize call traces covering UAF events
 - **[edge level] Cut-edge Coverage**: Cover edge destinations reaching targets
 - **[basic block level] Target Similarity**: Cover targets

★ Triage only **potential inputs** covering all locations & **pre-filter for free**

★ **Fast precomputation** at binary-level

UAF Bug Target

Stack Traces of CVE-2018-20623

// stack trace for the bad Use

```

==4440== Invalid read of size 1
==4440== at 0x40A8383: vfprintf (vfprintf.c:1632)
==4440== by 0x40A8670: buffered_vfprintf (vfprintf.c:2320)
==4440== by 0x40A62D0: vfprintf (vfprintf.c:1293)
[6] ==4440== by 0x80AA58A: error (elfcomm.c:43)
[5] ==4440== by 0x8085384: process_archive (readelf.c:19063)
[1] ==4440== by 0x8085A57: process_file (readelf.c:19242)
[0] ==4440== by 0x8085C6E: main (readelf.c:19318)
  
```

// stack trace for the Free

```

==4440== Address 0x421fdc8 is 0 bytes inside a block of size 86 free'd
==4440== at 0x402D358: free (in vgpreload_memcheck-x86-linux.so)
[4] ==4440== by 0x80857B4: process_archive (readelf.c:19178)
[1] ==4440== by 0x8085A57: process_file (readelf.c:19242)
[0] ==4440== by 0x8085C6E: main (readelf.c:19318)
  
```

// stack trace for the Alloc

```

==4440== Block was alloc'd at
==4440== at 0x402C17C: malloc (in vgpreload_memcheck-x86-linux.so)
[3] ==4440== by 0x80AC687: make_qualified_name (elfcomm.c:906)
[2] ==4440== by 0x80854BD: process_archive (readelf.c:19089)
[1] ==4440== by 0x8085A57: process_file (readelf.c:19242)
[0] ==4440== by 0x8085C6E: main (readelf.c:19318)
  
```


Dynamic Calling Tree

Bug Trace Flattening

UAF Bug Target:

0 (0x8085C6E, main) → **1** (0x8085A57, process_file) → **2** (0x80854BD, process_archive) → **3** (0x80AC687, make_qualified_name) → **4** (0x80857B4, process_archive) → **5** (0x8085384, process_archive) → **6** (0x80AA58A, error)

UAF-based Distance Metric

- Existing works compute seed distance
 - regardless of target ordering*
 - regardless of UAF characteristic: call traces may contain in sequence alloc/free function and reach use function*

- Intuition:** UAFuzz favors the **shortest** path that is likely to **cover more than 2 UAF events in sequence**
 - Statically identify and decrease weights of (caller, callee) in Call Graph
 - Ex: favored call traces $\langle main, f_2, f_{use} \rangle$, $\langle main, f_1, f_3, f_{use} \rangle$

Example of Call Graph, favored pairs (caller, callee) are in red

Cut-edge Coverage Metric

- Existing works *treat edges equally* in terms of reaching in sequence targets

- Cut-edge**
 - Edge destinations are more likely to **reach the next target** in the bug trace
 - Approximately identify via **static intraprocedural** analysis of CFGs
- Intuition:** UAFuzz favors inputs **exercising more cut edges** via a score depending on # covered cut edges and their hit counts

Control Flow Graph, cut edges are in blue

Target Similarity Metric

- Existing works select seeds to be mutated *regardless of number of covered target locations*

- Target Similarity Metric**
 - Prefix: more precise
 - Bag: less precise, but consider the whole trace
- Intuition:** Seed Selection heuristic based on both **prefix** and **bag** metrics
 - Select more frequently **max-reaching inputs** that have highest value of this metric (**most similar to the bug trace**) so far

trace of input s: 0 → 1 → 2 → 3 → 7 → 8 → 5

Bug Trace : 0 (alloc) → 1 → 2 (free) → 3 → 4 → 5 (use)

Power Schedule

Intuition: UAFuzz assigns more energy (a.k.a, # mutants) to

- seeds that are closer (using *UAF-based Distance*)
- seeds that are more similar to the bug trace (using *Target Similarity Metric*)
- seeds that make better decisions at critical code junctions (using *Cut-edge Coverage Metric*)

Pre-filter

- Existing works simply send *all* fuzzed inputs to the bug triager

- Potential inputs:** cover in sequence all target locations in the bug trace
- UAFuzz triages **only potential inputs** & **safely** discards others
 - Available for free after the fuzzing process via **Target Similarity Metric**
 - Saving a **huge amount of time** in bug triaging

Implementation

Support more open-source binary disassemblers

4. Experimental Evaluation

Evaluations

- Bug Reproduction
 - Time-to-Exposure, # bugs found, overhead, # triaging inputs
 - Patch-Oriented Testing
-
- Evaluated fuzzers
 - UAFuzz (BINSEC & AFL-QEMU)
 - AFL-QEMU
 - AFLGo (source - level) // Manh-Dung co-author
 - Our implementations AFLGoB & HawkeyeB
 - Benchmark
 - 13 UAF bugs of real-world programs

Bug Reproduction: Fuzzing Performance

- Total success runs vs. 2nd best
AFLGoB: **+34%** in total, up to +300%
- Time-to-Exposure (TTE) vs. 2nd best
AFLGoB: **2.0x**, avg 6.7x, max 43x
- Vargha-Delaney metric vs. 2nd best
AFLGoB: avg **0.78**

Bug-reproducing performance of binary-based DGFs

UAFuzz *outperforms* state-of-the-art directed fuzzers in terms of UAF bugs reproduction with a *high confidence level*

Bug Reproduction: Overhead

- Instrumentation overhead
 - **15x** faster in total than AFLGo-source
- Runtime overhead
 - UAFuzz has the same total executions done compared to AFL-QEMU

Global Overhead

UAFUZZ enjoys both a *lightweight instrumentation time* and a *minimal runtime overhead*

Bug Reproduction: Triage

- Total triaging inputs
 - UAFuzz only triages *potential* inputs (9.2% in total – sparing up to 99.76% of input seeds for confirmation)
- Total triaging time
 - UAFuzz only spends several seconds (avg 6s; 17x over AFLGoB, max 130x)

Bug Triage Performance

UAFuzz reduces a *large* portion (i.e., more than 90%) of triaging inputs in the post-processing phase

5. Patch-Oriented Testing

Patch-Oriented Testing

How to find

- Identify recently discovered UAF bugs
- Manually extract call instructions in bug traces
- Guide the directed fuzzer on the patch code

Targets

- Incomplete patches, regression bugs
- Weak parts of code

UAFuzz has been proven *effective in a patch-oriented* setting, allowing to find *30 new bugs (4 incomplete patches, 7 CVEs)* in 6 open-source programs

Patch-Oriented Testing: Zero-day Bugs

Program	Code Size	Version (Commit)	Bug ID	Vulnerability Type	Crash	Vulnerable Function	Status	CVE	
GPAC	545K	0.7.1 (987169b)	#1269	User after free	✗	gf_m2ts_process_pmt	Fixed	CVE-2019-20628	
		0.8.0 (56eaea8)	#1440-1	User after free	✗	gf_isom_box_del	Fixed	CVE-2020-11558	
		0.8.0 (56eaea8)	#1440-2	User after free	✗	gf_isom_box_del	Fixed	Pending	
		0.8.0 (56eaea8)	#1440-3	User after free	✗	gf_isom_box_del	Fixed	Pending	
		0.8.0 (5b37b21)	#1427	User after free	✓	gf_m2ts_process_pmt	✓		
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1263	NULL pointer dereference	✓	ilst_item_Read	✓	Fixed	
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1264	Heap buffer overflow	✓	gf_m2ts_process_pmt	✓	Fixed	CVE-2019-20629
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1265	Invalid read	✓	gf_m2ts_process_pmt	✓	Fixed	
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1266	Invalid read	✓	gf_m2ts_process_pmt	✓	Fixed	
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1267	NULL pointer dereference	✓	gf_m2ts_process_pmt	✓	Fixed	
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1268	Heap buffer overflow	✓	BS_ReadByte	✓	Fixed	CVE-2019-20630
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1270	Invalid read	✓	gf_list_count	✓	Fixed	CVE-2019-20631
		0.7.1 (987169b)	#1271	Invalid read	✓	gf_odf_delete_descriptor	✓	Fixed	CVE-2019-20632
		0.8.0 (5b37b21)	#1445	Heap buffer overflow	✓	gf_bs_read_data	✓	Fixed	
0.8.0 (5b37b21)	#1446	Stack buffer overflow	✓	gf_m2ts_get_adaptation_field	✓	Fixed			
GNU patch	7K	2.7.6 (76e7758)	#56683	Double free	✓	another_hunk	Confirmed	CVE-2019-20633	
		2.7.6 (76e7758)	#56681	Assertion failure	✓	pch_swap	Confirmed		
		2.7.6 (76e7758)	#56684	Memory leak	✗	xmalloc	Confirmed		
Perl 5	184K	5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134324	Use after free	✓	S_reg	Confirmed		
		5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134326	Use after free	✓	Perl_regnext	Fixed		
		5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134329	Use after free	✓	Perl_regnext	Fixed		
		5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134322	NULL pointer dereference	✓	do_clean_named_objs	Confirmed		
		5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134325	Heap buffer overflow	✓	S_reg	Fixed		
		5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134327	Invalid read	✓	S_regmatch	Fixed		
		5.31.3 (a3c7756)	#134328	Invalid read	✓	S_regmatch	Fixed		
		5.31.3 (45f8e7b)	#134342	Invalid read	✓	Perl_mro_isa_changed_in	Confirmed		
MuPDF	539K	1.16.1 (6566de7)	#702253	Use after free	✗	fz_drop_band_writer	Fixed		
Boolector	79K	3.2.1 (3249ae0)	#90	NULL pointer dereference	✓	set_last_occurrence_of_symbols	Confirmed		
fontforge	578K	20200314 (1604c74)	#4266	Use after free	✓	SFDGetBitmapChar			
		20200314 (1604c74)	#4267	NULL pointer dereference	✓	SFDGetBitmapChar			

Buggy Patch in GNU Patch CVE-2019-20633

```
==330== Invalid free() / delete / delete[] / realloc()
==330== at 0x402D358: free (in vgpreload_memcheck-x86-linux.so)
==330== by 0x8052E11: another_hunk (pch.c:1185)
==330== by 0x804C06C: main (patch.c:396)
==330== Address 0x4283540 is 0 bytes inside a block of size 2 free'd
==330== at 0x402D358: free (in vgpreload_memcheck-x86-linux.so)
==330== by 0x8052E11: another_hunk (pch.c:1185)
==330== by 0x804C06C: main (patch.c:396)
==330== Block was alloc'd at
==330== at 0x402C17C: malloc (in vgpreload_memcheck-x86-linux.so)
==330== by 0x805A821: savebuf (util.c:861)
==330== by 0x805423C: another_hunk (pch.c:1504)
==330== by 0x804C06C: main (patch.c:396)
```

*Using the bug trace of CVE-2018-6952 produced by Valgrind, we found an **incomplete fix** of GNU Patch with one different call in red*

6. Conclusion

Conclusion & Takeaways

- UAFuzz: A directed fuzzing framework to detect UAF bugs at binary level
- Find more bugs in bug reproduction than state-of-the-art tools
- New bugs and CVEs in patch-oriented testing

1. Directed Fuzzing exists, and it is **practical**
 - should **be integrated** into dev. process in addition to standard fuzzing
2. Recent trend **toward dedicated fuzzers** (UAFuzz, PerfFuzz, MemLock ...)
 - perform better than general fuzzers
3. Patch-oriented fuzzing is bigger than patch testing
4. Patching a PoC is not enough, we should find and fix **variants of the bug class**

Thank you ! Q & A

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**Paper:** Binary-level Directed Fuzzing for Use-After-Free Vulnerabilities (RAID'20)

**UAFuzz:** <https://github.com/strongcourage/uafuzz>

**UAF Fuzzing Benchmark:** <https://github.com/strongcourage/uafbench>

**BINSEC v0.3:** <https://binsec.github.io/>



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